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SHAPING EMPLOYEE BEHAVIOR THROUGH ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE: ROLE OF ANALYTICAL, CREATIVE PROBLEM-SOLVING AND PERSONAL STRESS-MANAGEMENT SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Manufacturing firms today operate in environments characterized by intense competition, rapid technological shifts, and rising performance expectations, making the role of employee behavior more critical. Many firms struggle with inconsistent problem-solving practices, limited creativity on the production floor, and growing stress levels among workers, all of which undermine productivity, quality, and operational reliability. Therefore, this study is an attempt to highlight the role of organizational culture in the promotion of employee behavior through solving problems analytically, solving problems creatively and managing personal stress. Three hundred and eighty-seven (387) responses were received through questionnaire survey and analyzed by using PLS-SEM. Results of the study demonstrated that organizational culture has significant contribution to the promotion of employee behavior. Furthermore, solving problems analytically and managing personal stress has direct as well as indirect effect of employee behavior. Organizational culture increases solving problems analytically and managing personal stress which further leads to organizational behavior. These findings contributed significantly to literature and provided valuable insights for policymakers.

KEYWORDS: Organizational Culture, Solving Problems Analytically, Solving Problems Creatively, Managing Personal Stress, Employee Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapidly developing technology, competition, and the growing need for efficiency, innovation, and adaptability among workforce have dramatically changed the way manufacturing operations of companies (Jahanshahi et al., 2025). Employee job roles have expanded to include ensuring operational excellence as manufacturing operations become more complicated (Liu et al., 2018; Tambunan et al., 2025). Employee behavior, such as responsibility, cooperation, adaptability, and commitment to their job responsibilities and tasks, is one of the major components contributing to the productivity, quality of product, and stability of an organization. The overall concept of organizational culture exists largely to shape employee thinking about problem-solving and challenges (Fadnavis et al., 2020) that occur in manufacturing environments based on shared values, norms, and behavioral expectations. Due to the dynamic and technical environment of modern manufacturing (Hu, 2023; Turkcan et al., 2022), it is critical to know how organizational culture has an impact on employee behavior from both an individual perspective as well as a cognitive perspective in order to maintain competitive advantage.

There are many organizational challenges facing manufacturing organizations with employee behaviors (Alieva & Powell, 2023; Jengwa & Chisoro, 2018) related to the following areas of concern: lack of compliance with manufacturing procedures, inability to make timely manufacturing decisions, a need for teamwork, and inconsistency in task performance from one employee to another. The focus of this study is employee behavior and is influenced by many different factors including problem-solving style, stress level, and the overall organizational climate. Most manufacturing companies experience inconsistent manufacturing performance (Arents & Greitans, 2022), lack of adaptability by their employees, conflict on workplace, and decreased employee engagement during times of high-stress production activity. All of these behavioral challenges can result in decreased production efficiency, increased rate of defects in manufactured products, increased operating expenses, and a higher level of safety risk. Employees continue to struggle to meet behavioral standards, even with appropriate training and supervision, especially when the performance of their job responsibilities becomes complicated due to a combination of factors including but not limited to complicated processes, tight time deadlines, and new manufacturing challenges. Therefore, it is important

for manufacturing firms to address the problems that arise from inconsistencies in employee behavior.

In previous studies, researchers have shown that the culture of an organization affects how employees behave (Purnama et al., 2024; Suharto & Nusantoro, 2018; Sumiyati et al., 2025). However, these studies have not conducted sufficient research to determine how organizational culture affects employee behavior by looking at the cognitive and emotional processes that mediate these relationships. The majority of prior research has focused on the service and corporate sector (Latif & Ullah, 2016; Øgaard et al., 2005; Yu Wang et al., 2025), and has thus not included how these relationships operate in manufacturing firms. These studies highlight the need for a more complete and integrated model that explains how the organizational culture interacts with employees' cognitive capabilities such as solving problems analytically, solving problems creatively and managing personal stress to produce their behavior.

Therefore, this study is an attempt to highlight the role of organizational culture in the promotion of employee behavior through solving problems analytically, solving problems creatively and managing personal stress. This research study has provided a broader explanation of how organizational culture translates to observable employee behavior by including the mediating variables of analytic and creative problem-solving and managing personal stress. This research also extends traditional culture-behavior models by integrating the cognitive (analytic and creative) and emotional (personal stress management) processes that are important in manufacturing firms. Empirically, this research provided evidence of the relationships examined in a sector that has received less attention in behavioral and managerial research. The expanded model developed in this research provides new theoretical perspectives and practical recommendations for utilizing cultural interventions and developing skills to enhance employee behavior. This research study supports manufacturing firms by providing a means of creating better and more effective work environments for their employees. Managers may create a culture that promotes structured thinking, creativity and emotional resilience, all of which are necessary for achieving competitiveness in modern manufacturing. The findings from this research study may also assist policymakers, industrial leaders and human resource professionals in understanding the behavioral challenges that they face and in improving productivity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. *Organizational Culture and Employee Behavior*

Organizational culture is the shared values, beliefs, and behaviors that guide how employees work, interact, and make decisions within a company (Nierenberg et al., 2017). It is one of the most important factors of employee competence (Cyfert et al., 2025). Therefore, employee behaviors are influenced by the way in which the employee perception of role, interaction with co-workers, and response to the organization requirements are shaped by the organization culture. A properly articulated and communicated culture that defines and outlines the organizational values, norms and acceptable behaviors creates valuable output for manufacturing firms. Research indicates that employees who incorporate the organization values of integrity, teamwork, accountability and customer focus into their daily work demonstrate a greater propensity towards cooperation, commitment and ethical behavior (Mercader et al., 2021). The culture also establishes informal guidelines for behavior, which dictate how employees communicate with each other, resolve conflict, and positively contribute to the achievement of the organizational goals. An inclusive and supportive culture fosters positive employee behaviors by creating an environment based upon trust, respect and psychological safety (Blom & Curseu, 2025), thereby empowering employees to demonstrate proactive and positive behaviors. Further, organizations with a culture of learning, openness and innovation tend to promote behavior among employees. Conversely, an organization with a weak or disconnected culture will often experience high levels of disengagement, employee resistance and counterproductive employee behaviors (Fridan & Maamari, 2024). Thus, organizational culture has a positive influence on employee behavior.

Hypothesis 1: Organizational culture has a positive effect on employee behavior.

2.2. *Organizational Culture, Solving Problems Analytically, Solving Problems Creatively and Managing Personal Stress*

An organizational culture is extremely important in shaping how people approach problem-solving (Bate, 1984), especially with analytical thinking. Therefore, it is imperative for an organization to develop a culture that encourages employees to approach problems analytically (Siswadi et al., 2023). Organizations where the culture promotes organized ways of thinking, evidence-based decisions, and a

commitment to continuous improvement, are more likely to have employees with higher performance. Based on earlier research, analytical thinking for problem-solving does not depend solely on the individual cognitive skills or instincts (De Jager et al., 2013) but is also contingent upon the context in which the information is processed. Organizations that value accuracy, motivate employees to assess alternative solutions, analyze reasons for the problem, and make their decisions based on data. Continued elements of a supportive organizational culture (Pool, 2000), such as the ability to share knowledge create cohesive cultures in which open communication and transparency encourage employees to think analytically. Several studies indicate that the analytical skills of employees improve when organizational norms promote discipline, clarity, and accountability. Therefore, a strong organizational culture lays the foundation for enhancing employees' cognitive and motivational capabilities toward the continual application of analytical thinking.

Hypothesis 2. Organizational culture has a positive effect on solving problems analytically.

Creative problem solving is a structured, imaginative process for tackling challenges by redefining problems, generating novel ideas, and implementing innovative solutions (Treffinger et al., 2023). An organizational culture that values creativity, flexibility, and openness will give employees the psychological space and the confidence to create and deliver novel and useful solutions (Ali Taha et al., 2016). An increase in the number of instances of creative problem-solving when rigid organizations decrease the number of rules that restrict creativity, support employees who take risks, and reward employees who generate innovative ideas. The dynamic nature of contemporary work environments will be enhanced when evasions of existing practices, questions of assumptions, and examination of alternative viewpoints are encouraged by a culture that promotes autonomy within the organizations. Additionally, cultures promoting collaborative and inclusive environments (Hudgins, 2012), where there is cross-functional exchange of ideas, enhance both the opportunities to engage in creativity and the development of a culture through exposure to different ideas. Although there are many examples of research supporting the idea that motivation leads to creative confidence (González-González & García-Almeida, 2021), which results in improved creative problem-solving capabilities. But a less supportive culture demotivates the employees. In short, the

cultural context in which an organization works is a significant factor influencing employees creative capabilities because it shapes the beliefs, values, and practices that support creativity.

Hypothesis 3. Organizational culture has a positive effect on solving problems creatively.

Organizational culture can significantly impact the employee ability to manage stress (Kim & Jung, 2022) by creating a psychological environment in the workplace. Supportive organizational cultures can create emotional well-being and provide coping resources for employees which reduces the level of stress (Sabuhari et al., 2020). Research supports that organizations with trust, open communication, and mutual respect will enable employees to have a greater perception of social support, a promising source for buffering stress (Zainab et al., 2022). The priorities of an organization on work-life balance, fairness, and the welfare of employees foster a culture that protect against burnout by creating a clear description between work and personal responsibilities. Research indicates that employees in a psychologically safe culture can seek assistance, share difficulties, and access stress-management services (Yadav & Pandita, 2025). In contrast, authoritarian and highly competitive cultures intensify anxiety, decrease coping skills and heighten chronic stress. Therefore, an organizational culture can play a pivotal role in an employee's ability to manage stress through emotional support.

Hypothesis 4. Organizational culture has a positive effect on managing personal stress.

2.3. Solving Problems Analytically, Solving Problems Creatively, Managing Personal Stress and Employee Behavior

Employee behavior is greatly influenced by analytical problem-solving abilities (Choi, 2022). Those who are more analytical tend to be methodical in identifying problems, reviewing important information and using logical reasoning to find solutions. Research has shown that people who think analytically make better decisions (Karenina et al., 2020), make fewer wrong decisions and act in a consistent and responsible manner at work than non-analyzers. Literature has also shown that those who think analytically can more effectively manage complex tasks and handle conflicts in a constructive way (Thompson & Johnson, 2014). Employee confidence levels also increase with analytical problem-solving practices because structured thinking allows for diminished uncertainty and thus will lead to more efficient performance. Therefore, companies that embrace a data-based decision-

making model generally report greater workplace behavior in terms of willingness to take responsibility for employee actions, maintain self-discipline and focus on completing tasks effectively. Analytical ability provides greater clarity in decision-making through improved error-reduction (Phillips et al., 2016) and thus promotes proactive behavior among employees. Thus, based on the above discussion, it is concluded that analytical problem-solving has a positive influence on employee behavior.

Hypothesis 5. Solving problems analytically has a positive effect on employee behavior.

Employees can utilize creativity to think differently and adapt as work conditions change while still being able to solve problems using innovative methods. Creative employees are usually proactive, able to overcome adversity and open to new ideas (Kapse et al., 2025; Yuming Wang et al., 2025). The behavioral outcomes of creative employees include increased collaboration, taking the initiative, and constructing input that is necessary for team problem-solving. Solving problems creatively also provides intrinsic motivation to employees (Dew, 2009; Martinsen & Furnham, 2019), as they feel engaged and empowered in the workplace. If the employees have a sense of ownership over their work, they are likely to cooperate, share knowledge, and communicate supportively with others. Companies that encourage creativity typically create an atmosphere of psychological safety for their employees to share their ideas and work confidently and ethically (Agarwal & Farndale, 2017). Additionally, creativity provides employees with the tools necessary to navigate the complexities of working in an organizational context, resolve conflicts through innovative ways, and provide input into the continuous improvement of organizational practices. Consequently, creative thinking promotes greater performance because it encourages behavioral patterns that support organizational goals.

Hypothesis 6. Solving problems creatively has a positive effect on employee behavior.

Stress management plays an important role in determining how employees behave at work (Murphy & Sorenson, 1988), as stress impacts an employee ability to regulate emotions, make decisions, and interact with other employees. Employees who manage their stress effectively can remain stable emotionally, exercise self-control, and think clearly when engaging in positive behavioral outcomes (Ebert et al., 2018). Studies indicate that by effectively managing their stress, employees are able

to remain focused, treat others with respect, and respond positively during challenging times (Desa et al., 2018; Pahi et al., 2016). If employees effectively cope with the challenges of their jobs, they are less likely to exhibit negative behaviors such as irritability, withdrawal from their peers, or lack of cooperation. Effective stress management improves employee well-being and job satisfaction (Wang & Gao, 2024), creating behaviors such as teamwork, taking responsibility, and being committed to an organization. Additionally, studies have shown that employees with high resilience and stress-management skills engage in ethical behavior, produce high levels of productivity, and demonstrate initiative in solving workplace problems. Conversely, unmanaged stress can lead to burnout, absenteeism, and counterproductive behaviors (Ybema et al., 2010). In conclusion, employees who successfully manage their stress have better cognitive and emotional resources to behave in ways that enable them to be successful in achieving organizational goals and developing positive working relationships.

Hypothesis 7. Managing personal stress has a positive effect on employee behavior.

2.4. Mediating Role of Solving Problems Analytically, Solving Problems Creatively and Managing Personal Stress

Organizational culture is the way in which organizations operate which provides a framework for employee cognitive and procedural development (Boan, 2006; Purnama et al., 2024). Evidence, clarity, and learning are the primary characteristics of a culture that utilizes evidence-based decision-making. As organizations develop culture that contains data-driven decisions and clearly defined procedures, that create an environment that encourages continuous improvement (Almeida et al., 2025; Chaudhuri et al., 2024). As a result, employees will learn to use systematic approaches to attain accurate and consistent actions based on solving problems which ultimately create behaviors. Therefore, analytical problem solving is the means by which organizational culture is converted to cognitive routines and decision making that affect the behaviors of the employees (Lehto et al., 2021). In terms of the relationship between employee behavior and organizational culture (Bindel Sibassaha et al., 2025; Praveena A & Fonceca, 2023; Ramadhani & Wardhani, 2024), this relationship can be examined by evaluating whether or not organizational culture is a statistically significant predictor of analytical problem solving, which is a statistically significant

predictor of employee behavior. Therefore, analytical problem-solving can be considered a mechanical, observable, empirical and testable mechanism through which organizational culture exerts its influence on employee behavior. Therefore, this discussion highlights that solving problems analytically has the potential to transfer the positive effect of organizational culture on employee behavior.

Hypothesis 8. Solving problems analytically mediates the relationship between organizational culture and employee behavior.

Creative problem solving is a channel through which an organizational culture affects how employees behave (Brown, 2003). If the culture within the organization provides support for discovery, allows for failure, values autonomy and promotes the sharing of ideas, it can create an environment conducive to experimenting with new ideas, allowing employees to combine existing knowledge and propose changes. Organizations can develop better employee behavior through various creative activities (Berg et al., 2017; Choi, 2022) such as creative thinking, proactivity, collaborative sharing of ideas and adaptive behavior in response to various changes. Similar with the current study, previous studies also highlighted the positive relationship between creativity, culture and employee behavior (Amiri et al., 2017; Makumbe, 2022). Furthermore, the basis of the mediation is twofold. First, the organizational culture creates an environment through the leadership encouragement of creativity for creative behavior. Second, creative behaviors create the opportunity for employees to be engaged in the process of creating or generating an idea and making it better through their interest and internal motivation. Mechanistic ways of how creativity will turn cultural signals into new behaviors by producing numerous response options and enhancing intrinsic motivation (Fischer et al., 2019). It is compulsory upon employees who create meaningful innovations to own their work and cooperate with others and exert a discretionary effort to improve their performance. Therefore, creative problem-solving is playing the role of mediating variable between organizational culture and employee behavior.

Hypothesis 9. Solving problems creatively mediates the relationship between organizational culture and employee behavior.

It is important to consider that stress management is the mediator between organizational culture and behavior since culture sets psychosocial work environment of an individual, which can act as a

protective buffer against stress or increase an employee exposure. Organizational cultures that offer support, fairness, clear role expectations (Chandler et al., 2000; Pool, 2000), and a balance between work and personal life can reduce chronic stress and aid employees in developing a number of coping resources such as social support, autonomy in the workplace, and access to well-being programs. Conversely, organizational cultures that are extremely high-pressure and ambiguous (Robertson & Swan, 2003), will compound the number of stressors an employee must face and hinder an employee ability to self-regulate (Ogbeibu et al., 2020). When employees learn how to effectively manage their own stress, they can utilize their cognitive functions at a higher level, regulate their emotions more effectively, and work more cooperatively and consistently with others (Wren,

2020). The process of how the culture creates the mediating effect is the following: the culture provides or denies resources and norms for coping, therefore creating the stress management capability that ultimately determines how consistent an employee behavior will be and how engaged the employee will become in pro-social behaviors. Thus, according to the evidence from the literature, stress management is a robust theoretical mediator between supportive organizational cultures and employee behavior.

Hypothesis 10. Managing personal stress mediates the relationship between organizational culture and employee behavior.

Based on the above hypotheses development, the current study proposed the framework shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Framework of the Study.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Questionnaire Development

This study examined the relationship between organizational culture, solving problems analytically, solving problems creatively, managing personal stress and employee behavior, as shown in Figure 1. Nature of this study relationship is consistent with the questionnaire survey. Therefore, this study developed a questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. Questionnaire was adapted from previous studies by making minor changes to scale items. Employee behavior is considered in relation to citizenship behavior of employees and scale items are adapted from Buil et al. (2016). Furthermore, operationalization of solving problems analytically, solving problems creatively and managing personal stress is based on Pedraza-Rodríguez et al. (2023). Minor changes were made in

the scale items. Scale items for employee behavior was adapted from Buil et al. (2016). All the scale items are reported in Table 2 along with individual item reliability.

3.2. Sample Size and Population

Sample size for this study was calculated based on the total population of the study. Manufacturing firms are considered in this study, and data was collected from the employees. All types of manufacturing companies such as pharmaceuticals and healthcare, oil and gas, food and beverage, chemicals, construction and cement, textiles and apparel, steel and heavy machinery and consumer goods were considered. According to Krejcie and Morgan (1970), sample size should not be less than 384, if the population is higher than 10,000. Since the population in the current study is higher than 10,000, therefore, this study decided 384 as appropriate

sample size.

3.3. Data Collection Procedure and Response Rate

The population of this study spreads to a wide geographical area. To cover the whole population, this study employed area cluster sampling which is recommended by Sekaran and Bougie (2010). Whole population was divided into various clusters, and few clusters were chosen randomly. Finally, questionnaires were distributed randomly among the employees of pharmaceuticals and healthcare, oil and gas, food and beverage, chemicals, construction and cement, textiles and apparel, steel and heavy machinery and consumer goods. Questionnaires were distributed online as well as self-visits to various companies. Three reminders were sent to respondents who did not respond to the survey. Out of 800 distributed questionnaires, 395 were returned, however, eight questionnaires were incomplete and

excluded from the study. Finally, 387 questionnaires were used in data analysis with response rate of 48.3% which is acceptable.

3.4. Data Screening and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Data screening was carried out to remove the errors in the data such as missing value and outlier. Furthermore, data normality was also examined. While data screening, no missing value and outlier was found. However, data was slightly non-normal which was managed by using Smart PLS. As it is recommended in the previous studies, Smart PLS is suitable to handle non-normal data and provide original results (Hair Jr et al., 2016). Furthermore, variance inflation factor (VIF) was considered to check the issue of multicollinearity. According to Kock (2015), VIF values should be less than 3.3. As reported in Table 1 and Figure 2, all the values of VIF are less than 3.3.

Table 1: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF).

Constructs	VIF
Organizational Culture	2.93
Solving problems Analytically	1.89
Solving problems Creatively	2.25
Managing personal Stress	2.81

Figure 2: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF).

4. DATA ANALYSIS

This study assessed PLS measurement model to confirm the authenticity of scale used for data collection. The PLS measurement model evaluates how well the survey items represent the underlying constructs in a study (Hair Jr et al., 2022). Once the measurement model meets the required criteria, researchers can confidently move to the structural

model for hypothesis testing (Edeh et al., 2023; Hair Jr et al., 2016). Convergent validity was assessed by using PLS measurement model as shown in Figure 3. To evaluate the convergent validity, average variance extracted (AVE), composite reliability (CR) and factor loadings were used. All of the factors in Table 2 were higher than the suggested value of 0.70 for every item. Therefore, factor loading confirmed the reliability of all scale items.

Table 2: Convergent Validity.

Construct	Items	Factor Loadings
Organizational Culture (OC)	1. The company information is clear and straightforward.	0.925
	2. The company's reports are written in clear and easy-to-understand language.	0.925
	3. The format of company accounting data makes complex information easy to grasp.	0.94
	4. Company communication aids quick, effective decision making.	0.918
Solving Problems Analytically (SPA)	1. I state what the problem is before solving.	0.717
	2. I see more than one alternative solution.	0.887
	3. I keep steps in the problem-solving process.	0.886
	4. I try out several definitions of the problem.	0.894
	5. I have lots of questions about the problem.	0.889
	6. I think about the problem logically and intuitively.	0.877
	7. I evaluate the solution with many options.	0.865
	8. I develop creative and innovative solutions	0.868
Solving Problems Creatively (SPC)	1. I make sure to get divergent points of view.	0.882
	2. I get information from outside the organization.	0.882
	3. I provide recognition for those who provide ideas.	0.891
	4. I encourage in pursuit of creative solutions.	0.889
Managing Personal Stress (MPS)	1. I use effective time-management methods.	0.85
	2. I frequently affirm my priorities.	0.87
	3. I maintain a program of regular exercise.	0.881
	4. I maintain an open, trusting relationship.	0.904
	5. I practice temporary relaxation techniques.	0.875
	6. I maintain balance in my life	0.899
Employee Behavior (EB)	1. I am willing to give my time to help others who have work-related problems.	0.949
	2. I provide time to help others who have work problems.	0.939
	3. I assist other employees in their tasks related to their duty.	0.934

Figure 3: PLS Measurement Model.

Furthermore, every CR value was higher than the suggested threshold of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2017). Additionally, every AVE value for every understudy construct above the suggested threshold of 0.50 (Hair Jr et al., 2016). Cronbach's alpha (α) was used to assess the instrument reliability. According to Hair, Black, Babin and Anderson (2010), reliability in the range of 0.70 is deemed acceptable, reliability below 0.60 is deemed weak, and reliability over 0.80 is deemed good. The Cronbach's coefficient (α) estimates for all variables were greater than 0.80 which was considered good.

After confirmation of convergent validity, this study examined the discriminant validity. According to the literature, discriminant validity should be assessed by using two way: AVE square root and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of correlations (HTMT) (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, et al., 2010). HTMT is the latest criteria which is used in this study. According to Hafkesbrink (2021), none of HTMT value should exceed 0.9. Table 4 shows that all the values are less than 0.9 which confirmed discriminant validity.

Table 3: Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR) and AVE.

Construct	α	Composite Reliability	AVE
Employee Behavior	0.935	0.959	0.885
Managing Personal Stress	0.942	0.954	0.774
Organizational Culture	0.945	0.961	0.859
Solving Problems Analytically	0.951	0.959	0.748
Solving Problems Creatively	0.909	0.936	0.785

Table 4: HTMT_{0.9}.

Construct	Employee Behavior	Managing Personal Stress	Organizational Culture	Solving Problems Analytically	Solving Problems Creatively
Employee Behavior					
Managing Personal Stress	0.782				
Organizational Culture	0.766	0.737			
Solving Problems Analytically	0.684	0.794	0.806		
Solving Problems Creatively	0.776	0.804	0.743	0.686	

Hypotheses of the study were examined by using PLS structural model which is shown in Figure 4. T-value 1.96 and p-value 0.05 was considered a minimum threshold level to accept the hypotheses. According to the results reported in Table 5, managing personal stress has a significant and positive effect on employee behavior ($\beta = 0.927$, $T = 29.223$, $p = 0$). Organizational culture also significantly and positively influences employee behavior ($\beta = 0.253$, $T = 8.612$, $p = 0$). Furthermore, it is found that organizational culture demonstrates significant and positive effect on managing personal

stress ($\beta = 0.702$, $T = 30.425$, $p = 0$). Organizational culture has significant and positive effect on solving problems analytically ($\beta = 0.778$, $T = 30.781$, $p = 0$) and solving problems creatively ($\beta = 0.687$, $T = 19.175$, $p = 0$). It is found that solving problems analytically significantly contributes to employee behavior ($\beta = 0.239$, $T = 5.086$, $p = 0$), whereas solving problems creatively shows no significant effect on employee behavior ($\beta = 0.004$, $T = 0.07$, $p = 0.944$). According to these results, out of seven direct effect hypotheses, six hypotheses were found significant, however, one was insignificant.

Table 5: Path Coefficient (Direct Effect).

Relationship	β	STDEV	T Value	P Values	Decision
Managing Personal Stress -> Employee Behavior	0.927	0.032	29.223	0	Supported
Organizational Culture -> Employee Behavior	0.253	0.029	8.612	0	Supported
Organizational Culture -> Managing Personal Stress	0.702	0.023	30.425	0	Supported
Organizational Culture -> Solving Problems Analytically	0.778	0.025	30.781	0	Supported
Organizational Culture -> Solving Problems Creatively	0.687	0.036	19.175	0	Supported
Solving Problems Analytically -> Employee Behavior	0.239	0.047	5.086	0	Supported
Solving Problems Creatively -> Employee Behavior	0.004	0.05	0.07	0.944	Not Supported

Figure 4: PLS Structural Model.

This study examined three indirect effects of solving problems analytically, solving problems creatively and managing personal stress between organizational culture and employee behavior. The indirect effect of solving problems analytically between organizational culture and employee behavior ($\beta = 0.186, T = 4.95, p = 0$) found significant. However, the indirect effect of solving problems

creatively between organizational culture and employee behavior ($\beta = 0.002, T = 4.95, p = 0$) found insignificant. Finally, the indirect effect of managing personal stress between organizational culture and employee behavior found significant ($\beta = 0.651, T = 22.22, p = 0.944$). Indirect effect results are presented in Table 6 and also shown with histogram which is reported in Figure 5.

Table 6: Path Coefficient (In-direct Effect).

Relationship	β	STDEV	T Values	P Values	Decision
Organizational Culture -> Managing Personal Stress -> Employee Behavior	0.651	0.029	22.22	0	Supported
Organizational Culture -> Solving Problems Analytically -> Employee Behavior	0.186	0.038	4.95	0	Supported
Organizational Culture -> Solving Problems Creatively -> Employee Behavior	0.002	0.035	0.07	0.944	Not Supported

Figure 5: Indirect Effect Histogram.

5. DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to highlight the role of organizational culture in the promotion of employee behavior through solving problems analytically, solving problems creatively and managing personal stress. The relationship between organizational culture, solving problems analytically, solving problems creatively, managing personal stress and employee behavior was considered by using 10 hypotheses, including seven direct effect and three indirect effects. Results of the study validated eight hypotheses; however, two hypotheses were rejected.

The research supports the hypothesis 1 that organizational culture has a positive impact on employee behavior by demonstrating that culture provides guidance to employees in terms of their actions and interactions based upon shared values, norms and expectations across the organization. To provide employees with clarity, purpose and direction there needs to be an organizational culture that is both supportive, collaborative and structured (Weare et al., 2014). A strong organizational culture will result in improved cooperation, ethical conduct and responsible working behaviors (Roy et al., 2024; Terec-Vlad & Cucu, 2016). As demonstrated by the significant statistical results of this study, cultural values have a direct impact on how employees respond to their work tasks and how they interact with other employees. Based upon the results of the current study it can be inferred that employees become socialized into the organizational culture and as such will develop and exhibit behaviors that are consistent with the expectations and values associated with that culture. Similarly, other studies also reported the positive relationship between organizational culture and employee behavior (Iqbal & Parray, 2025; Praveena A & Fonceca, 2023). In addition, the results of this study provide further evidence that organizational culture can be utilized as a mechanism of social control to align individual behaviors with the goals of the organization. The findings support the notion that organizational culture is a fundamental driver of employee behavioral outcomes in the organizational context.

Results of hypothesis 2 show that organizational culture significantly contributes to the promotion of analytical problem-solving. Cultures that are highly structured, clear, supportive of learning and facilitate an evidence-based decision-making environment will naturally help to create a culture where employees will engage in a systematic way of addressing challenges. As indicated by the

significance of relationships, organizational norms have a strong effect upon the way in which employees process information, evaluate the options available to them and make rationally-based decisions. The findings are consistent with the literature in that organizational culture provides the framework within which employees have the cognitive capability to think analytically (Boan, 2006; Hartnell et al., 2011). Employees operating within environments characterized by strong organizational structure and knowledge-based systems (Forte et al., 2016; Khaksar et al., 2023) are more likely to rely on systematic reasoning, thereby leading to fewer errors made along with the development of more effective solutions to their problems. The findings indicate that building on the cultural values of discipline, accuracy, and continual improvement is important for organizations. Hypothesis 2 validates that analytical problem-solving is not only an individual ability but also a product of the way organizations are designed and how the organizational cultural values are reflected and reinforced.

Furthermore, the findings support the hypothesis 3 that organizational culture has a positive and strong impact on creative problem-solving. Culture that supports the development and acceptance of innovation, autonomy, collaboration, and the willingness to take risks creates the psychological safety necessary for employees to use their imagination and creativity by experimenting with new ideas. This supports the previous reasonings that creativity can be encouraged only when employees are in an open, supportive, respectful, and collaborative environment, where employees feel empowered to take creative action to solve problems creatively. All of the evidence supported the conclusion that when employees perceive their work environment as being supportive of their development and success (Kundu & Lata, 2017; Yuzliza et al., 2021), they are more likely to engage in creativity and the development of creative solutions for the problems. Similarly, previous studies highlighted the positive relationship between organizational culture and employee creativity (Ali Taha et al., 2016; Ogbeibu et al., 2024; Sumiyati et al., 2025).

Hypothesis 4 highlighted that organizational culture enhances the ability of employees to manage personal stress. The results of this study align with previous research indicating that diverse, healthy, and supportive cultures have a positive impact on employees' perceptions of being engaged in the positive and supportive work environment (Aboobaker & Shanujas, 2025; Lowe et al., 2003;

Zalesny et al., 1985). Employees in positive culture also possess better abilities to regulate their emotions. The presence of strong leadership support, open lines of communication, and a trusting atmosphere creates an excellent opportunity for employees to navigate pressure in the best possible way. This illustrates the impact of a company's culture on decreasing the risk of employee burnout and anxiety, as well as increasing an employee's overall well-being.

The results of the study confirm hypothesis 5 that analytical problem-solving is a significant contributor to positive employee behavior. Employee behavior was observed to exhibit consistency and productivity through structured and logical thinking in their work. Consequentially, the analytical process reduces impulsive, rash responses from employees allowing for accountability on behalf of the employee. These results are consistent with previous studies that support analytical thinkers in making informed decisions (Elson et al., 2018; Kallet, 2014), following organizational policies and processes. The statistically significant results provide evidence that analytical problem-solving produces clarity, decreases errors, and produces employee behavior consistent with organizational expectations. However, results of hypothesis 6 shows insignificant relationship, therefore, determined that creative problem-solving is not significantly related to employee behavior within the same organizational context. This finding is inconsistent with most studies that relate creative thinking to positive employee behavior (Basadur et al., 2000; Jiang & Yang, 2015; Tan et al., 2023). One potential explanation for this difference is that although employees engage in creative thinking, it may not lead them to behavior that can directly be observed, or more specifically, engaged in structured environments where creative approaches may be difficult. In addition, as creativity often requires some level of risk-taking, this behavior might not fit with an employee expected behavioral norm and may lead them to not act upon a creative idea. Additionally, the insignificant impact indicates that even though organizational culture may encourage creativity, there are no existing systems within the organization to promote and reward these behaviors. Moreover, the results of hypothesis 7 confirm that employees who effectively manage stress will have a greater impact on their behaviors at the workplace than employees who are not successful in managing their stress. Such employees continue to behave in an appropriate and professional manner and are more

focused, calm and cooperative. As such, employees will develop healthy interpersonal relationships, as well as develop productive work habits. These findings, thus, support previous studies that indicate that managing stress improves emotional stability (Alessandri et al., 2018; Strizhitskaya et al., 2019). When employees manage stress effectively, they are able to effectively cope with their workload pressure without becoming frustrated, distracted or unable to do their job, resulting in more accountable and consistent behaviors. Therefore, these results confirmed the importance of mental well-being as a factor shaping workplace behavior.

Additionally, this study examined the indirect effect through hypothesis 8, hypothesis 9 and hypothesis 10. The results of hypothesis 8 highlighted that analytical problem solving mediates the relationship between organizational culture and employee behavior. Culture has an impact on how people think about problems analytically and therefore ultimately influences how they act. Because of this, culture will influence employees in ways that shape their personal behavioral outcomes directly through analytical thinking and indirectly through other ways. Therefore, the significance of mediation validates that culture influences behavior in an indirect manner via cognitive means. However, hypothesis 9 was not supported, which indicates that creative problem solving does not mediate the relationship between culture and employee behavior. Although culture statistically significantly improves creativity (Hypothesis 3), creativity, in itself, did not produce a statistically significant influence on employee behavior (Hypothesis 6), indicating that there is no evidence to support the pathway through which creativity is thought to mediate the relationship between culture and employee behavior. This theoretical rejection of the hypothesis is justified because creativity does not necessarily lead to behavior change, especially in work environments where creativity is celebrated from a culture perspective but does not become part of a day-to-day process. Finally, the findings from hypothesis 10 of this study support the statement that how employees manage the impact of personal stress influences the relationship between culture and employee behavior. Supportive and equitable cultural contexts enhance the ability for employees to successfully cope with stress and, as such, decreased levels of personal stress led to higher levels of stable, cooperative, and productive behavior. Therefore, the mediation outcome would appear to validate the assumption that employees how they manage the impact of personal stress would act as the key means

by which culture translates into employee behavior.

5.1. Implications of the Study

This study provides theoretical evidence that analytical problem-solving serves as a stronger mechanism than creative thinking for translating culture into behavior within manufacturing environments. The study confirms that managing personal stress is a key mediator in manufacturing, offering new theoretical insights into how emotional regulation influences behavioral stability on factory floors. Furthermore, the findings support that culture affects employees differently depending on operational demands, extending culture theory by showing stronger effects on analytical rather than creative cognitive processes in manufacturing. These findings extend behavior theories by showing that behavior is shaped by how employees mentally process tasks under cultural expectations in fast-paced production systems. Additionally, the rejection of creative problem-solving effect highlights a theoretical boundary condition: creativity does not always predict behavior in highly regulated manufacturing contexts, suggesting that creativity behavior theories require contextual refinement. Similarly, the rejected mediation of creativity introduces theoretical limits to mediation models in industries where deviation from standard procedures is discouraged.

Aforementioned theoretical implications lead to the important practical implications. For instance, manufacturing firms should invest more in analytical problem-solving training since it directly improves behavior, unlike creative training. Firms should embed cultural values into problem-solving protocols because culture strongly shapes analytical reasoning. Since creativity does not translate into behavior, performance metrics should reward precision, compliance, and analytical accuracy rather than idea generation. Additionally, stress should be treated as a behavioral risk factor because employees who manage stress behave more safely and reliably

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REFERENCES

- Aboobaker, N., & Shanujas, V. (2025). Towards a sustainable workplace: Investigating workplace cyberbullying and its relationship with employee wellbeing and intention to stay in remote and hybrid work settings. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 74(2), 453–470.
- Agarwal, P., & Farndale, E. (2017). High-performance work systems and creativity implementation: The role of psychological capital and psychological safety. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(3), 440–458.

in the workplace. Supervisors should be trained to consistently communicate cultural norms, as culture directly influences behavior and cognitive processes in manufacturing settings. On the other hand, since creativity does not affect behavior, creative tasks should be placed in controlled innovation units or improvement teams rather than routine operational roles. Finally, a culture that supports learning increases analytical reasoning; manufacturing firms can enhance behavior by integrating engineers, supervisors, and floor workers in joint learning forums.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Despite the imperative contribution of this study to theory and practice, there are minor limitations which lead to direction for future studies. For example, this study focuses only on manufacturing firms, where standardized production processes may limit the natural expression of creative problem-solving compared to service sectors, potentially constraining the variability of key constructs. Hence, future studies should consider service firms or make a comparison between manufacturing firms and service firms. Additionally, data were collected during routine production periods rather than peak or low-demand seasons; employee stress, creativity, and behavior may differ under fluctuating workloads. Therefore, future studies should select a specific production period to examine the relationship between variables. Manufacturing firms differ significantly in automation, which may influence employee opportunities to engage in analytical and creative problem-solving but were not controlled in the model. It is better to use control variables before data collection. Furthermore, employees working different shifts (morning, evening, night) may experience varying levels of stress and cognitive engagement, however this study did not stratify the sample by shift patterns. Consequently, future studies should be careful while collecting data from the employees of different shifts.

- Alessandri, G., Perinelli, E., De Longis, E., Schaufeli, W. B., Theodorou, A., Borgogni, L., ... Cinque, L. (2018). Job burnout: The contribution of emotional stability and emotional self-efficacy beliefs. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 91(4), 823–851.
- Ali Taha, V., Sirkova, M., & Ferencova, M. (2016). The impact of organizational culture on creativity and innovation. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 14.
- Alieva, J., & Powell, D. J. (2023). The significance of employee behaviours and soft management practices to avoid digital waste during a digital transformation. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*, 14(1), 1–32.
- Almeida, A. S. d., Kock, N., & Zanini, M. T. (2025). Fostering public sector innovation: How data-driven organizational culture influences exploitation innovations. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 29(4), e240179.
- Amiri, S. R. S., Qayoumi, A., & Soltani, M. (2017). Study the relationship between organization culture and employee's creativity in cultural organizations: A case study. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Oman Chapter)*, 6(10), 1–8.
- Arents, J., & Greitans, M. (2022). Smart industrial robot control trends, challenges and opportunities within manufacturing. *Applied Sciences*, 12(2), 937.
- Basadur, M., Runco, M. A., & Vegaxy, L. A. (2000). Understanding how creative thinking skills, attitudes and behaviors work together: A causal process model. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 34(2), 77–100.
- Bate, P. (1984). The impact of organizational culture on approaches to organizational problem-solving. *Organization Studies*, 5(1), 43–66.
- Berg, S. T. S., Grimstad, A., Škerlavaj, M., & Černe, M. (2017). Social and economic leader-member exchange and employee creative behavior: The role of employee willingness to take risks and emotional carrying capacity. *European Management Journal*, 35(5), 676–687.
- Bindel Sibassaha, J. L., Pea-Assounga, J. B. B., & Bambi, P. D. R. (2025). Influence of digital transformation on employee innovative behavior: Roles of challenging appraisal, organizational culture support, and transformational leadership style. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, 1532977.
- Blom, A. B., & Curseu, P. L. (2025). A multilevel investigation of the relationship between the strength of ethical organizational culture and psychological safety: Do simple organizational interventions work? *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 38(2), 378–392.
- Boan, D. M. (2006). Cognitive-behavior modification and organizational culture. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 58(1), 51–60.
- Brown, J. G. (2003). Creativity and problem-solving. *Marquette Law Review*, 87, 697–719.
- Buil, I., Martínez, E., & Matute, J. (2016). From internal brand management to organizational citizenship behaviours: Evidence from frontline employees in the hotel industry. *Tourism Management*, 57, 256–271.
- Chandler, G. N., Keller, C., & Lyon, D. W. (2000). Unraveling the determinants and consequences of an innovation-supportive organizational culture. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 25(1), 59–76.
- Chaudhuri, R., Chatterjee, S., Vrontis, D., & Thrassou, A. (2024). Adoption of robust business analytics for product innovation and organizational performance: The mediating role of organizational data-driven culture. *Annals of Operations Research*, 339(3), 1757–1791.
- Choi, S. B. (2022). When and how does leader feedback promote employee creative problem-solving behavior? A three-way interaction model of employee feedback acceptance and task complexity. *Journal of Korean Society for Quality Management*, 50(4), 777–792.
- Cyfert, S., Dyduch, W., Szumowski, W., & Prause, G. (2025). Are we ready for digital transformation? The role of organizational culture, leadership and competence in building digital advantage. *Central European Management Journal*, 33(2), 219–231.
- De Jager, C., Muller, A., & Roodt, G. (2013). Developing creative and innovative thinking and problem-solving skills in a financial services organisation. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 11(1), 1–10.
- Desa, N. M., Khoon, T. L., Hasmi, M., & Asaari, A. H. (2018). Work stress toward work environment, management support, and employee satisfaction among employees of public organizations. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 8(1), 1–11.
- Dew, R. (2009). Creative resolve response: How changes in creative motivation relate to cognitive style. *Journal of Management Development*, 28(10), 945–966.
- Ebert, D. D., Kählke, F., Buntrock, C., Berking, M., Smit, F., Heber, E., Lehr, D. (2018). A health economic outcome evaluation of an internet-based mobile-supported stress management intervention for employees. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*, 171–182.

- Elson, S. B., Hartman, R., Beatty, A., Trippe, M., Buckley, K., Bornmann, J., ... Lee, J. (2018). Critical analytic thinking skills: Do they predict job-related task performance above and beyond general intelligence? *Personnel Assessment and Decisions*, 4(1), 2–14.
- Fadnavis, S., Najarzadeh, A., & Badurdeen, F. (2020). An assessment of organizational culture traits impacting problem solving for lean transformation. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 48, 31–42.
- Fischer, C., Malycha, C. P., & Schafmann, E. (2019). The influence of intrinsic motivation and synergistic extrinsic motivators on creativity and innovation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 137.
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 39–50.
- Forte, P., Hoojaghan, F. A., & Pool, J. K. (2016). Investigating the effect of organisational culture on knowledge management and performance: An empirical study in knowledge-based companies using the balanced scorecard. *International Journal of Management and Decision Making*, 15(2), 167–183.
- Fridan, A. A. A., & Maamari, B. E. (2024). Impact of organizational positive and negative culture on employee performance. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 32(9), 1850–1869.
- González-González, T., & García-Almeida, D. J. (2021). Frontline employee-driven innovation through suggestions in hospitality firms: The role of the employee's creativity, knowledge, and motivation. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 94, 102877.
- Hafkesbrink, J. (2021). Questions: Heterotrait–Monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) in assessing the discriminant validity in PLS-SEM model? *ResearchGate* (12 February 2022).
- Hair, J., Hollingsworth, C. L., Randolph, A. B., & Chong, A. Y. L. (2017). An updated and expanded assessment of PLS-SEM in information systems research. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 117(3), 442–458.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis*. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage Publications. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acclit.2016.09.003>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2022). *Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using R: A workbook*. Springer Nature.
- Hartnell, C. A., Ou, A. Y., & Kinicki, A. (2011). Organizational culture and organizational effectiveness: A meta-analytic investigation of the competing values framework's theoretical suppositions. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96(4), 677.
- Hu, C. (2023). Analyzing dynamic coupling and coordination of modern service and advanced manufacturing industries in Guangdong–Hong Kong–Macao Greater Bay Area. *Heliyon*, 9(6).
- Hudgins, K. S. (2012). Creating a collaborative and inclusive culture for students with special education needs. *McNair Scholars Research Journal*, 5(1), 8.
- Iqbal, J., & Parray, Z. A. (2025). Striking the balance: Unraveling the influence of organizational culture on organization citizenship behavior with corporate social responsibility as the bridge. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 74(6), 2091–2112.
- Jahanshahi, A. A., Cakir, F. S., Kalaycioglu, O., & Adiguzel, Z. (2025). Driving innovation from within: The role of a supportive workplace in fostering managerial innovation in Turkey's export-oriented machinery sector. *Middle East Journal of Management*, 12(1), 124–150.
- Jengwa, E., & Chisoro, M. L. (2018). Evaluation into the impact of employee behaviour on productivity at a manufacturing company. *Journal of Marketing and HR (JMHR)*, 7(1), 422–439.
- Jiang, J., & Yang, B. (2015). Roles of creative process engagement and leader–member exchange in critical thinking and employee creativity. *Social Behavior and Personality: An International Journal*, 43(7), 1217–1231.
- Kallet, M. (2014). *Think smarter: Critical thinking to improve problem-solving and decision-making skills*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kapse, M., Jain, P. S., Pathak, A., Poulouse, J., & Sharma, V. (2025). Intrinsic motivational factors and creative and innovative work behaviour of employees: The mediating effect of creative personality. *International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management*, 34(4), 481–503.
- Karenina, A., Widoretno, S., & Prayitno, B. A. (2020). Effectiveness of problem solving-based module to improve analytical thinking. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*.

- Khaksar, S. M. S., Chu, M.-T., Rozario, S., & Slade, B. (2023). Knowledge-based dynamic capabilities and knowledge worker productivity in professional service firms: The moderating role of organisational culture. *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, 21(2), 241–258.
- Kim, J., & Jung, H.-S. (2022). The effect of employee competency and organizational culture on employees' perceived stress for better workplace. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(8), 4428.
- Kock, N. (2015). Common method bias in PLS-SEM: A full collinearity assessment approach. *International Journal of e-Collaboration (IJEC)*, 11(4), 1–10.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607–610.
- Kundu, S. C., & Lata, K. (2017). Effects of supportive work environment on employee retention: Mediating role of organizational engagement. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 25(4), 703–722.
- Latif, K. F., & Ullah, M. (2016). An empirical investigation into the relationship between organizational culture, internal service quality (ISQ) and organizational performance. *Abasyn University Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(1).
- Lehto, M. R., Nanda, G., & Nanda, G. (2021). Decision-making models, decision support, and problem solving. In *Handbook of human factors and ergonomics* (pp. 159–202).
- Liu, M., Huang, Y., & Zhang, D. (2018). Gamification's impact on manufacturing: Enhancing job motivation, satisfaction and operational performance with smartphone-based gamified job design. *Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing & Service Industries*, 28(1), 38–51.
- Lowe, G. S., Schellenberg, G., & Shannon, H. S. (2003). Correlates of employees' perceptions of a healthy work environment. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 17(6), 390–399.
- Makumbe, W. (2022). The impact of organizational culture on employee creativity amongst Zimbabwean academics. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 14(2), 523–531.
- Martinsen, Ø. L., & Furnham, A. (2019). Cognitive style and competence motivation in creative problem solving. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 139, 241–246.
- Mercader, V., Galván-Vela, E., Ravina-Ripoll, R., & Popescu, C. R. G. (2021). A focus on ethical value under the vision of leadership, teamwork, effective communication and productivity. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(11), 522.
- Murphy, L. R., & Sorenson, S. (1988). Employee behaviors before and after stress management. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 9(2), 173–182.
- Nierenberg, B., Alexakis, G., Preziosi, R. C., & O'Neill, C. (2017). Workplace happiness: An empirical study on well-being and its relationship with organizational culture, leadership, and job satisfaction. *International Leadership Journal*, 9(3), 2–23.
- Øgaard, T., Larsen, S., & Marnburg, E. (2005). Organizational culture and performance: Evidence from the fast food restaurant industry. *Food Service Technology*, 5(1), 23–34.
- Ogbeibu, S., Pereira, V., Burgess, J., Gaskin, J., Emelifeonwu, J., Tarba, S. Y., & Arslan, A. (2024). Responsible innovation in organisations: Unpacking the effects of leader trustworthiness and organizational culture on employee creativity. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 41(3), 947–977.
- Ogbeibu, S., Senadjki, A., & Gaskin, J. (2020). Organisational cultures and the evoked effects of leader ability on employee creativity. *American Journal of Business*, 35(3/4), 153–173.
- Pahi, M. H., Hamid, K. A., & Khalid, N. (2016). Save talent of banking sector of Pakistan: Mediating job satisfaction between job stress and employee turnover intention. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(3), 617–624.
- Pedraza-Rodríguez, J. A., Ruiz-Vélez, A., Sánchez-Rodríguez, M. I., & Fernández-Esquinas, M. (2023). Management skills and organizational culture as sources of innovation for firms in peripheral regions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 191, 122518.
- Phillips, W. J., Fletcher, J. M., Marks, A. D., & Hine, D. W. (2016). Thinking styles and decision making: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 142(3), 260.
- Pool, S. W. (2000). The learning organization: Motivating employees by integrating TQM philosophy in a supportive organizational culture. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 21(8), 373–378.
- Praveena A, A., & Fonceca, C. M. (2023). Organizational culture and its influence on employee behavior. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 14.

- Purnama, C., Fatmah, D., Rahmah, M., Hasani, S., Rahmah, Y., & Rahmah, Z. Z. (2024). Understanding how organizational culture and job satisfaction drive commitment and citizenship behavior in SMEs. *Journal of HRM*, 27(2).
- Ramadhani, F., & Wardhani, N. K. (2024). The influence of organizational culture and organizational commitment on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) of employees of government sector with work engagement mediation. *Dinasti International Journal of Education Management & Social Science*, 5(6).
- Robertson, M., & Swan, J. (2003). 'Control-what control?' Culture and ambiguity within a knowledge intensive firm. *Journal of Management Studies*, 40(4), 831-858.
- Roy, A., Newman, A., Round, H., & Bhattacharya, S. (2024). Ethical culture in organizations: A review and agenda for future research. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 34(1), 97-138.
- Sabuhari, R., Sudiro, A., Irawanto, D., & Rahayu, M. (2020). The effects of human resource flexibility, employee competency, organizational culture adaptation and job satisfaction on employee performance. *Management Science Letters*, 10(8), 1775-1786.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2010). Theoretical framework. In *Research methods for business: A skill building approach* (p. 80).
- Siswadi, Y., Jufrizen, J., Saripuddin, J., Farisi, S., & Sari, M. (2023). Organizational culture and organizational citizenship behavior: The mediating role of learning organizations and organizational commitment. *Jurnal Riset Bisnis Dan Manajemen*, 16(1), 73-82.
- Strizhitskaya, O., Petrash, M., Savenysheva, S., Murtazina, I., & Golovey, L. (2019). Perceived stress and psychological well-being: The role of emotional stability. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 56.
- Suharto, S., & Nusantoro, J. (2018). The relationship among managerial capability, organizational citizenship behavior, and employee performance: Mediation effects of organizational culture. *Journal of Community Research and Service*, 2(1), 168-175.
- Sumiyati, S., Riyanto, A. S., Zaharuddin, Z., & Supriyadi, S. (2025). Organizational culture and emotional intelligence on employee creativity. *International Journal of Business, Law, and Education*, 6(1), 326-331.
- Tambunan, H. N., Haribowo, R., Akbar, A., Munizu, M., & Pandiangan, S. M. T. (2025). Operational management for business production processes. *International Journal of Education, Social Studies, and Management (IJESSM)*, 5(1), 161-169.
- Tan, A. B., van Dun, D. H., & Wilderom, C. P. (2023). Lean innovation training and transformational leadership for employee creative role identity and innovative work behavior in a public service organization. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*, 15(8), 1-31.
- Terec-Vlad, L., & Cucu, M. (2016). Ethics and organizational culture: Key elements regarding the development of economic activities. *Ecoforum Journal*, 5(1), 8.
- Thompson, V. A., & Johnson, S. C. (2014). Conflict, metacognition, and analytic thinking. *Thinking & Reasoning*, 20(2), 215-244.
- Treffinger, D. J., Isaksen, S. G., & Stead-Dorval, K. B. (2023). *Creative problem solving: An introduction*. Routledge.
- Turkcan, H., Imamoglu, S. Z., & Ince, H. (2022). To be more innovative and more competitive in dynamic environments: The role of additive manufacturing. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 246, 108418.
- Wang, X., & Gao, Y. (2024). Analyzing the effectiveness of workplace stress management programs on employee well-being and productivity in Chinese corporations. *American Journal of Health Behavior*, 48(5), 1354-1367.
- Wang, Y., Arshad, M. Z., & Arshad, D. (2025). Proactive eco-initiatives in healthcare: Exploring the role of motivation, organizational culture, and leadership. *Acta Psychologica*, 255, 104921.
- Wang, Y., Luo, J., & Hu, W. (2025). Proving my creativity: When and why leaders' idea rejection leads to employees' creative deviance? *Personality and Individual Differences*, 233, 112881.
- Weare, C., Lichterman, P., & Esparza, N. (2014). Collaboration and culture: Organizational culture and the dynamics of collaborative policy networks. *Policy Studies Journal*, 42(4), 590-619.
- Wren, D. (2020). The culture of UK employee-owned worker cooperatives. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*, 42(3), 761-776.
- Yadav, A., & Pandita, D. (2025). Do employees feel psychologically safe? Assessing its linkage with psychological well-being. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 1-18.

- Ybema, J. F., Smulders, P. G., & Bongers, P. M. (2010). Antecedents and consequences of employee absenteeism: A longitudinal perspective on the role of job satisfaction and burnout. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology, 19*(1), 102–124.
- Yusliza, M. Y., Noor Faezah, J., Ali, N. A., Mohamad Noor, N. M., Ramayah, T., Tanveer, M. I., & Fawehinmi, O. (2021). Effects of supportive work environment on employee retention: The mediating role of person–organisation fit. *Industrial and Commercial Training, 53*(3), 201–216.
- Zainab, B., Akbar, W., & Siddiqui, F. (2022). Impact of transformational leadership and transparent communication on employee openness to change: Mediating role of employee organization trust and moderated role of change-related self-efficacy. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal, 43*(1), 1–13.
- Zalesny, M. D., Farace, R. V., & Kurchner-Hawkins, R. (1985). Determinants of employee work perceptions and attitudes: Perceived work environment and organizational level. *Environment and Behavior, 17*(5), 567–592.